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Abstract

STUDIES ON THE INTERACTION OF HYDRAZINE AND ASPARTIC ACID TOWARDS SOME TRANSITION METALS AND THEIR BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITIES

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Objective - Literature survey indicates that hydrazine the simplest diamine, is known to form fairly stable complexes with mineral and carboxylic acids. Among the different substituted dicarboxylic acids, the potential tridentate α -amino dicarboxylic acid such as aspartic acid has been found to exhibit a strong interaction towards metal ions. Though the interaction of aspartic acid with aromatic amines, imidazole, bipyridine and phenanthroline towards various metals has been well studied, the studies with simple diamine, hydrazine with the metals in the medium of aspartic acid however have not yet been established. Hence objective is to prepare metal hydrazine / hydrazinium α -amino dicarboxylates and to study its elemental analysis, thermal decomposition patterns, isomorphism, and hence to propose the structure, and also to study the bactericidal activities of the ligands.

Design / Methodology/ Approach- The present paper is based on primary data. These complexes were characterized by different physico-chemical studies and tested for their toxicity towards bacteria.

Findings- New aspartate complexes of some transition metals with hydrazinium cation, $N_2H_5M(Asp)_{1.5}0.5H_2O$ where $M= Co, Ni, Zn$ or Cd have been prepared. The complexes were found to be octahedron around each metal ion. The dicarboxylic acids are dianionic in nature and contains non-coordinated hydrazinium cation. Water is present as a lattice molecule. Mostly, all the complexes undergo two step decomposition yielding metal oxide as the final residue. The complexes are isomorphous, not only within, but also in between the series. Most of the tested compounds are effective bactericides.

Practical implications- Detailed study on biocidal activities makes the compound use as an effective bactericides.

Scope for future work- Various biological studies can be carried out using these complexes

Key words: Aspartic acid, hydrazine, TG-DTA , XRD and biocidal activities.

INTRODUCTION

Hydrazine is the simplest diamine and forms salt with mineral and carboxylic acids [6,7,15,12,24]. The interaction of hydrazine towards metal ions in the presence of carboxylate system has opened up a new

area of coordination chemistry due to its versatility in coordination. The monoprotonated hydrazine, the hydrazinium cation still retains a basic site and hence capable of coordination with various metal ions. However, many hydrazinium complexes reported in the literature contain hydrazinium ion as a mere charge neutralizing species [2,16]. The complexes containing coordinated hydrazinium ion are used as very good precursor for the preparation of nanoparticles [19] with nearly uniform particle size. Some of these salts are used as flame-retardants [11,12] and proton conductors [4].

Among the different substituted dicarboxylic acids, the potential tridentate acid such as aspartic acid has been found to exhibit a strong interaction towards metal ions both in solution [8] and in solid state via their two carboxyl and one central amino binding donors. Further it is known that the amino acids, the protein building blocks are biologically active and myriad of biological functions performed by metallo proteins, has evolved very few ligands to coordinate with the metal ions. Of these few types of biological ligands, aspartate side chains form an important class. Studies have also proved that in biological processes, calcium ions commonly exert their effects by binding to proteins normally via aspartate or glutamate residues.

OBJECTIVE

Though the interaction of aspartic acid with aromatic amines, imidazole, bipyridine and phenanthroline towards various metals has been well studied, the studies with simple diamine, hydrazine with the metals in the medium of aspartic acid however have not yet been established unambiguously.

Therefore, based on the importance and recent surge of interest, has prompted to synthesize complexes of transition metals with aspartic acid in the presence of hydrazine and the present study has been focused with following objectives.

1. To prepare metal hydrazine / hydrazinium α -amino dicarboxylates by the reaction of metal carbonates and the acid with hydrazine hydrate.
2. To study the nature of interaction of hydrazine / hydrazinium moieties and amino acids in the above complexes and their thermal decomposition.
3. To correlate the structure and thermal reactivity among the complexes.
4. To study the isomorphism among the complexes.
5. To propose the structure for the complexes tentatively from the available data.
6. To study the bacterial activities of the ligands and complexes.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Hydrazine, also called as dinitrogen tetrahydride, is the simplest diamine. The great growth of interest and the versatility of hydrazine molecule are due the presence of two free electron pairs and four substitutable hydrogen atoms, in addition to the potential N-N bond. Bibliographic works on hydrazine have been done by Audrieth and Ogg, Clark, Bottomley, and Schmidt [1,3,5,15]

Hydrazine, besides its use in the synthetic organic chemistry has been utilised in the fields of inorganic chemistry, coordination chemistry and material science with different motives. Hydrazine, N_2H_4 can act as a neutral monodentate, bidentate and bridged bidentate ligand during its complexation with metal carboxylates. Furthermore, even in weakly acidic medium it generates hydrazinium cation, $N_2H_5^+$ which is also capable of coordination with metal ions. The form and nature of hydrazine in complexes greatly influences the structure, thermal stability,

solubility and biological activity of the hydrazine metal carboxylates.

Literature survey clearly reveals that plenty of hydrazine complexes of transition metal carboxylates [17,18,20,22,23] have been prepared and their spectral and thermal properties have been exhaustively studied. However, only few aromatic carboxylic acid complexes have been investigated because of their complicated multi-stage thermal degradation patterns [9,10,26]. The presence of both nitro group and hydrazine in these complexes lead to one or two step decomposition at quite lower temperatures.

The IR spectra of hydrazine, its salts and metal complexes are studied in the finger print region 1300 and 650 cm^{-1} . In the various complexes examined $\nu_{\text{N-N}}$ could be found at the following frequency ranges [2].

N_2H_4 (in solid state)	875 cm^{-1}
N_2H_4 (monodenate)	930-940 cm^{-1}
N_2H_4 (bridging)	948-985 cm^{-1}
H_2NNHY (Y= COO,CSS)	986-1012 cm^{-1}
N_2H_5^+ (non-coordinated)	960-970 cm^{-1}
N_2H_5^+ (coordinated)	990-1015 cm^{-1}
$\text{N}_2\text{H}_6^{2+}$ (monodenate)	1020-1045 cm^{-1}

Though, the N-N stretching for the free N_2H_5^+ and the bridging N_2H_4 overlap, they can be identified by fixing the composition by analytical and other techniques.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Preparation of $\text{N}_2\text{H}_5\text{M}(\text{Asp})_{1.5}0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ [where M= Co, Ni, Zn or Cd] and Asp= $\text{OOC-CH}_2\text{-CH-COO}^-$

An aqueous suspension (10ml) containing stoichiometric mixture of aspartic acid (0.665g) and corresponding metal carbonates [CoCO_3 (0.5g), $\text{NiCO}_3 \cdot 2\text{Ni}(\text{OH})_2$ (0.5g), CdCO_3 (0.5g), $\text{ZnCO}_3 \cdot \text{ZnO} \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.5g)] were stirred in a magnetic stirrer for one hour maintained at 80°C. The solution was then filtered, cooled and a methanolic solution (25ml) of hydrazine hydrate (15ml) was added and kept in a water bath for 5 minutes. The complexes formed were washed with absolute alcohol and dried in vacuum.

Physico-Chemical studies

The metal content in all the complexes were determined by EDTA complexometric titrations after decomposing a known amount of the complex with concentrated nitric acid. The hydrazine content was estimated volumetrically using KIO_3 solution (0.025 mol) under Andrew's condition.

A Perkin-Elmer CHN analyser (Model 240B) was used for C, H and N analysis. The IR spectra of the complexes were recorded on a SHIMADZU (8201) spectrophotometer using KBr pellets in the range 4000-400 cm^{-1} . The room temperature magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out with Gouy balance using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{SCN})_4]$ as a calibrant. The simultaneous TG-DTA of the complexes in air was carried out using TG/DTA STA 1500 Thermal Analyser. The heating rate employed was 20°C / min using platinum cups as sample holders. X-ray powder diffraction pattern of samples were obtained using SHIMADZU (Lab-6000). Antibacterial studies for the complexes have been carried out.

ANALYSIS

Aspartate complexes of some transition metals with hydrazinium cation, $N_2H_5M(Asp)_{1.5} \cdot 0.5H_2O$ where $M = Co, Ni, Zn$ or Cd have been prepared by stirring an aqueous suspension containing mixture metal carbonates and aspartic acid in a magnetic stirrer, to which methanolic solution of hydrazine hydrate was added.

All the complexes are slightly hygroscopic and can be generated after dissolving them in water. The complexes are stable when stored in desiccator.

The amino acid gave the single compositional metal complexes with with a mono hydrazinium cation and half a molecule of water, as hydrazinium metal α -amino dicarboxylate hemihydrate. The chemical analysis (Table.1) confirm the proposed composition. The intense blue, pink colour of the nickel and cobalt complexes, respectively are indicative of octahedral coordination around Ni(II) and Co(II) metal ions.

Table.1
Analytical data

Compound	Hydrazine %		Metal %		Carbon %		Hydrogen %		Nitrogen %		Yield
	Obs	Cal	Obs	Cal	Obs	Cal	Obs	Cal	Obs	Cal	
$N_2H_5Co(Asp)_{1.5} \cdot 0.5H_2O$	10.7	10.7	20.1	19.7	23.3	24.2	4.6	4.5	17.5	16.4	70
$N_2H_5Ni(Asp)_{1.5} \cdot 0.5H_2O$	11.0	10.7	19.5	19.7	22.2	24.2	4.4	4.5	17.9	16.4	75
$N_2H_5Zn(Asp)_{1.5} \cdot 0.5H_2O$	10.7	10.5	22.0	21.5	25.0	23.6	4.0	4.4	16.0	16.1	60
$N_2H_5Cd(Asp)_{1.5} \cdot 0.5H_2O$	8.5	9.11	31.8	32.0	22.0	20.5	3.6	3.8	13.6	13.9	62

Magnetic measurements

The zinc and cadmium complexes are diamagnetic as expected, whereas for the nickel and cadmium complexes, the room temperature magnetic values coincide with the Van Vleck [25] values. The cobalt aspartate complex have magnetic moment 4.80 B.M, and for the Ni(II) complex the value is 2.90 B.M, suggesting an octahedral geometry.

Infrared spectra

The infrared spectral data of all the complexes are summarized in Table -2 and assigned on the basis of earlier studies [2,4,11,21]. The infrared spectra of the complexes are also given in

Figs. 1-4 to compare with the data. The complexes exhibit a sharp band of medium intensity in the range, 3400-3380 cm^{-1} due to O-H stretching confirming the presence of water molecule. In the 3340-3157 cm^{-1} region, the IR spectra of the compounds show medium intensity bands corresponding to N-H stretching frequencies of hydrazine and amino groups. The carboxyl asymmetric and symmetric stretchings are observed as a broad band centered in the range, 1591-1556 and 1419-1398 cm^{-1} , respectively with a $\Delta\nu$ ($\nu_{\text{asym}} - \nu_{\text{sym}}$) separation between 193-154 cm^{-1} . The broad and split bands in the complexes indicate the complex nature of coordination of the two carboxyl groups towards the metals. However, the bands indicate the ionization of two carboxyl groups leading to complex formation and also these bands are mixed modes with that of NH_2 bending frequencies of hydrazine and amino group of α - amino acid. From the carboxyl stretches, different modes of coordination of two carboxyl groups are suspected. And also, based on the border line $\Delta\nu$ values around 170 cm^{-1} suggest, both unidentate and bidentate chelating coordination of the carboxylate groups[11]. The N-N stretching frequency is observed in the range, 970-945 cm^{-1} , which coincides with the N-N stretching of the non-coordinated nature of N_2H_5^+ cation [2].

Table-2
Infrared spectral data (cm^{-1})

Compound	ν_{OH} of H_2O	$\nu_{\text{N-H}}$	ν_{asym} (OCO)	ν_{sym} (OCO)	$\Delta\nu$	$\nu_{\text{N-N}}$
$\text{N}_2\text{H}_5\text{Co}(\text{Asp})_{1.5}0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	3440	3318 3285 3186	1585	1419	166	961
$\text{N}_2\text{H}_5\text{Ni}(\text{Asp})_{1.5}0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	3420	3340 3200(b) 3173	1583	1418	163	953
$\text{N}_2\text{H}_5\text{Zn}(\text{Asp})_{1.5}0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	3400	3275 3157	1591	1398	193	970
$\text{N}_2\text{H}_5\text{Cd}(\text{Asp})_{1.5}0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	3410	3287 3157	1556	1402	154	962

Fig -1 IR spectra for $N_2H_5Co(Asp)_{1.5}0.5H_2O$

Fig-2 IR spectra for $N_2H_5Ni(Asp)_{1.5}0.5H_2O$

Fig-3 IR spectra of $N_2H_5Zn(Asp)_{1.5}0.5H_2O$

Fig-4 IR spectra for $N_2H_5Cd(Asp)_{1.5}0.5H_2O$

Thermal decomposition studies

The data of the thermally studied complexes are listed in Table-3. The composition of the anhydrous intermediate and the final products are best fit with the observed mass losses in TG. Thermogravimetric results are in good agreement with the DTA endothermic and exothermic temperatures.

$N_2H_5M(Asp)_{1.5} \cdot 0.5H_2O$ [where M= Co or Zn]

The TG of the complexes exhibit two steps of decomposition in accordance with the DTA showing an endotherm and exotherm respectively [2,24]. The first endotherm observed around 80°C with a mass loss of 3.00% is attributed to the loss of half a molecule of water. Such a low temperature endothermic dehydration indicates the presence of water as a lattice molecule. The anhydrous hydrazinium metal aspartate intermediate undergoes a continuous exothermic decomposition in a single step to yield the metal oxide as the stable residue. The decomposition of both the complexes are completed within 500°C.

Table-3
Thermal data

Compound	DTA peak Temp. °C	Thermogravimetry (TG)			Decomposition product
		Temp. Range °C	Mass loss (%)		
			Obsd	Calcd.	
$N_2H_5Co(Asp)_{1.5} \cdot 0.5H_2O$	72(+) 376(-)	52-95 95-385	03.50 71.00	3.03 73.09	$N_2H_5Co(Asp)_{1.5}$ Co_3CO_4
$N_2H_5Zn(Asp)_{1.5} \cdot 0.5H_2O$	80(+) 467(-)	58-105 105-490	03.00 65.00	02.96 73.23	$N_2H_5Zn(Asp)_{1.5}$ ZnO

Fig-5 TG-DTA for $N_2H_5Co(Asp)_{1.5} \cdot 0.5H_2O$

Fig-6 TG-DTA for $N_2H_5Zn(Asp)_{1.5}0.5H_2O$

X-ray powder diffraction studies

The patterns of the aspartate complexes are given in Fig-7. The patterns reveal that the complexes are isomorphous, not only within, but also between the series. This clearly shows that the anion does not affect the overall structure and have the similar mode of coordination. The ‘d’ spacings of specific intense peaks of the complexes are summarized in Table-4. The peaks are not well resolved which may be due to the powdery nature of the complexes.

Table-4
 XRD data of aspartate complexes
 (d-spacings in Å°)

$N_2H_5Co(Asp)_{1.5}0.5H_2O$	$N_2H_5Ni(Asp)_{1.5}0.5H_2O$	$N_2H_5Zn(Asp)_{1.5}0.5H_2O$	$N_2H_5Cd(Asp)_{1.5}0.5H_2O$
-	-	-	-
-	12.17	-	12.21
-	-	-	-
9.90	-	-	-
8.96	-	8.77	-
-	8.52	-	-
-	7.79	-	-
4.79	4.30	-	3.39

Fig-7 X-ray powder diffractograms of aspartate complexes

Biocidal activities

The aspartate complexes were tested for their growth inhibitory activity against bacteria named Pseudomonas Fluorescence and fungi namely Aspergillus Flavus. The inhibition of bacterial and fungal growth measured as the radius of the zone of inhibition is tabulated as follows.

Screening for the antibacterial activity.

Compound	Zone of inhibition	
	50%	100%
Aspartic acid	NI	NI
$N_2H_5Co(Asp)_{1.5} \cdot 0.5H_2O$	14	17
$N_2H_5Ni(Asp)_{1.5} \cdot 0.5H_2O$	17	19
$N_2H_5Cd(Asp)_{1.5} \cdot 0.5H_2O$	12	14
$N_2H_5Zn(Asp)_{1.5} \cdot 0.5H_2O$	16	18

NI-no inhibition

Legends of the photographs for antibacterial studies are listed below

1. Aspartic acid
2. $N_2H_5Ni(Asp)_{1.5}0.5H_2O$
3. $N_2H_5Co(Asp)_{1.5}0.5H_2O$
4. $N_2H_5Cd(Asp)_{1.5}0.5H_2O$
5. $N_2H_5Zn(Asp)_{1.5}0.5H_2O$

Screening for the antibacterial activity at 50% and 100% concentration

CONCLUSION

Aspartate complexes of some transition metals with hydrazinium cation, $N_2H_5M(Asp)_{1.5}0.5H_2O$ where $M= Co, Ni, Zn$ or Cd have been synthesized and characterized by IR spectra, TG-DTA, magnetic moments and XRD. The complexes are also tested for their toxicity towards bacteria. Magnetic moment measurements and colour of the complexes indicate the octahedron around each metal ion. IR spectra reveal the dianionic nature of the dicarboxylic acids and non-coordinated hydrazinium cation. The low temperature dehydration and mass loss observed from the thermal studies ascertain the presence of water as a lattice molecule. Mostly, all the complexes undergo two step decomposition yielding metal oxide as the final residue. The XRD patterns show that the complexes are isomorphous, not only within, but also in between the series. Most of the tested compounds are effective bactericides.

SCOPE FOR FUTURE WORK

Most of the tested compounds are effective bactericides. Detailed study on biocidal activities have a great scope for further research.

REFERENCES

1. Audrieth, L.F. and Ogg, B.A. (1951), "The Chemistry of Hydrazine", John Wiley, New York.
2. Braibanti, A., Dallavalle, F., Pellinghelli, M.A. and Leporati, E. (1968), "The nitrogen-nitrogen stretching band in hydrazine derivatives and complexes", *Inorganic Chemistry*, Vol. 7, No. 7, pp. 1430–1433.
3. Bottomley, F. (1974), *Quart.Rev.,Chem.SOC.*,Vol. 24, pp. 617.
4. Chandra, S. and Singh, N. (1983), "Fast-proton transport in hydrazine sulphate. II. NMR linewidth and relaxation studies", *Journal of Physics C*, Vol. 16, No. 16, pp. 3081.
5. Clark, C.C.(1953), "Hydrazine", Mathieson.Chem. Corp. Baltimore,Md.
6. Govindarajan, S., Patil, K.C., Poojary, M.D. and Monohar, H. (1986), "Synthesis, characterization and X-ray structure of hexahydrazinium diuranil penta-oxalate dihydrate, $(N_2H_5)_6(UO_2)_2(C_2O_4)_5 \cdot 2H_2O$ ", *Inorganica Chimica Acta*, Vol. 120, No. 1, pp. 103–107.
7. Govindarajan, S., Patil, K.C., Monohar, H. and Werner, P.E, (1986), "Hydrazinium as a ligand - structural, thermal, spectroscopic, and magnetic studies of hydrazinium lanthanide di-sulfate monohydrates - crystal-structure of the neodymium compound", *Journal of the Chemical Society-Dalton Transactions*, No. 1, pp. 119–123.
8. Kanomari, K., Teraoka, M., Maeda, H. and Okamoto, K. (1993),*Chem. Lett.*, 1731.
9. Kuppusamy, K. and Govindarajan, S. (1995), *Eur. J. Solid State Inorg. Chem.*, Vol. 32, pp. 997-1012.
10. Kuppusamy, K. and Govindarajan, S. (1996), *Thermochimica Acta*, Vol. 274, pp. 125-138.
11. Nakamoto, K. (1978), "Infrared and Raman spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", 3rd Edition, Wiley/Interscience, New York.
12. Patil, K.C., Soundararajan, R. and Pai Verneker, V. R. (1979), "Synthesis and characterization of a new fluoride derivative of hydrazine, hydrazinium bifluoride", *Inorganic Chemistry*, Vol. 18, No. 7, pp. 1969–1971.
13. Patil, K.C., Vittal, J.P. and Patel, C.C. (1980), "Monohydrazinium phosphate as flame retardant", *The Journal of fire retardant chemistry*, Vol. 7, pp. 3–8.
14. Patil, K.C., Vittal, J.P. and Patel, C.C. (1981), "Pyrolysis and combustion of α -cellulose: effect of dihydrazinium phosphate $(N_2H_5)_2HPO_4$ ", *Thermochimica Acta*, Vol. 43, No. 2, pp. 213–219.
15. Schmidt, E.W. (1984), "Hydrazine and its Derivatives-Preparation, Properties and Applications", Wiley Interscience, New York, NY, USA.
16. Sharmila, J.R. and Sivasankar, B.N. (2004), "New hydrazinium lanthanide sulphite hydrates", *Journal of Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry*, Vol. 78, No. 3, pp. 933–940.
17. Sivasankar, B.N. and Govindarajan, S. (1994), *Synth. React. Inorg. Met-Org. Chem.*, Vol. 24, No. 9, 1573–1582.
18. Sivasankar, B.N. and Govindarajan, S. (1997), *J. Therm. Anal.*, Vol. 48, pp.1401-1413.
19. Thangavelu, K., Parameswari, K., Kuppusamy, K. and Haldorai, Y. (2011), "A simple and facile method to synthesize Co_3O_4 nanoparticles from metal benzoate dihydrazinate complex as a precursor", *Materials Letters*, Vol. 65, No. 10, pp. 1482–1484.
20. Yasodhai, S. and Govindarajan, S. (1999), *J. Therm. Anal. and cal.*, , 62 737-745.
21. Yasodhai, S. and Govindarajan, S. (1999), "Preparation and thermal behaviour of some hydrazinium dicarboxylates," *Thermochimica Acta*, Vol. 338, No. 1-2, pp. 113–123.
22. Yasodhai, S. and Govindarajan, S. (1999), *Synth. React. Inorg. Met-Org. Chem.*, Vol. 29 No. 6, 919-934.
23. Yasodhai, S. and Govindarajan, S. (2000), *Synth. React. Inorg. Met-Org. Chem.*, Vol. 30, No. 4, 7455-760.
24. Yasodhai, S., Sivakumar, T. and Govindarajan, S. (1999), "Preparation, characterisation and thermal reactivity of transition metal complexes of hydrazine with citric acid", *Thermochimica Acta*, Vol. 338, No. 1-2, pp. 57–65.
25. Van Vleck, J.H. and Frank, A. (1929), *Phys.Rev.*,Vol. 34, pp. 1494,1625.
26. Vikram, L. and Sivasankar, B.N. (2007), *Thermochimica Acta*, Vol. 452, pp. 20-27.